

DEVELOPMENT OF ANTI-TONZILITIC AND ANTI-MOLCHE TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. As a result of the research, the composition of a caramel paste against tonsillitis and expectoration based on a decoction of walnuts and pomegranate peel was developed. At the same time, a method for preparing the caramel mass, adding it to the medicinal product, and a technological scheme for the pastille were proposed.

Keywords. Pastila, walnuts, pomegranate peel, decoction, tannin, tannins.

Introduction. A complication of diseases of the upper respiratory tract, such as bacteriological and viral inflammation of the throat, tonsillitis, pharyngitis, influenza (acute respiratory infections), allergic cough, is a chronic cough with severe pain, which is now widespread among the population.

According to statistics from the World Health Organization (WHO), tonsillitis, inflammation of the throat, affects 10-15% of the world's population, including 20-25% of young children. Due to insufficient attention to this disease, in 99% of developing countries, deaths from acute inflammation of the upper respiratory tract affecting the lower respiratory tract are observed in children under 5 years of age [1].

Currently, the use of plant raw materials in the production of medicines is common as an alternative to synthetic drugs. The pharmacological effect of preparations based on plant materials is not inferior to synthetic drugs, and their side effects are relatively insignificant. Today, 112 species of medicinal plants grow in Uzbekistan, of which 70 are used in the pharmaceutical industry [2].

The medicinal form of Pastilla has been used to treat throat infections since ancient times (1000 BC). The earliest version of this remedy was made in Egypt using various products such as honey, medicinal herbs, citrus fruits, and spices. These pastilles were modified by the Smith Brothers in 1852 and by Luden in 1879. To increase the effectiveness of the pastilles, a small amount of heroin and morphine was added to their composition [3].

Materials and methods of research. To obtain a decoction of pomegranate peel and walnut leaves in a 1:10 ratio, the AU-3 (Russia) infusion apparatus was used. Electronic scales VK-300.1 were used to determine the average weight of the pastila. The tannin content of the pastilles was determined by permanganometry, and the moisture content of the finished product was determined on the "MB35" Ohaus Corp. equipment from China.

Results. The initial stage of the research began with the preparation of pomegranate peel (*Punica Granatum L.*) raw materials. This variety was chosen due to the high content of tannin in the hard-shelled "tuya tish" variety of pomegranate with a sour taste. After separating the bark of both plants and drying at room temperature, a decoction was prepared in an infusion apparatus in a 1:10 ratio. Caramel pastries were prepared based on the decoction. To prevent the viscosity of the sugar syrup from increasing, apple cider vinegar was added to its

composition. Our caramel paste was prepared by pouring into molds. The molds were cleaned and lubricated with vegetable oil for better separation of the pastilles from the mold.

Conclusion. As a result of the research, the optimal composition of a caramel paste from a decoction of pomegranate peel and walnuts was selected, and a technology was developed. The quality of the resulting paste was evaluated.

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